

Audio-Lingual Method: Impact on English Speaking in Bengali-Medium Schools.

Author

Mr.Pradip Kumar Mahata

Faculty of English at Garhbeta College
Paschim Medinipur, West Bengal.

Research Scholar at C V Raman Global University, Bhubaneswar, Odisha

Co-Author

Prof.(Dr).Pragyan Paramita Pattnaik

Professor and Head of the Department of English.
CGU, Bhubaneswar, Odisha

Article History

Volume 4, Issue 4, 2022

Received: 16 May 2022

Accepted: 25 June 2022

Doi:

10.48047/AFJBS.4.4.2022.599-608

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to explore the influence of the audio-lingual method on the instruction of English as a Second Language (ESL) in schools that utilize Bengali as the primary medium of instruction. Bengali-medium students are not able to learn English using the audio-lingual method at present. The aim of this investigation is to test the efficacy of audio-lingual methods in Bengali and other vernacular-medium schools in Jhargram District, West Bengal. Will it be possible to execute successfully in these schools? This research has been conducted to find the answer to the question. Researchers used a method called a "quasi-experimental study" to conduct the study. The researcher had selected 40 students in 10th and 12th grades to study the impact. The learners were sorted into "experimental" and "control" groups. Three distinct tools were used to collect the data: a pre-test, a post-test, and a questionnaire. Then, a descriptive analysis of the data was performed to reach a feasible solution to the problem.

Keywords – Audio lingual Method, Secondary Education, Speaking English.

INTRODUCTION

Swami Vivekananda once said, "Education is the manifestation of the perfection already in man." The purpose of education is to reveal the nature of human conduct. Language learning is essential to academic success. When two guys want to communicate with one another, they resort to language. Approximately half of the World's population has used English as their primary language. English as a Second Language (ESL) teaching is a difficult task, especially in a multi-lingual country like India. As a technique of education, this choice

is crucial since it ensures that the learner acquires proficiency in the target language. Through memorization and repetition, students learn the strategy and can eventually use it as their native tongue.

Everyday human interaction necessitates some form of linguistic exchange; indeed, life and language are inseparable, language is the medium through which human ideas are exchanged. Learning a language is an important life skill that begins when children are infants and continues through the preschool years. (Muliadi, 2018; Muliadi, Suparlan 2019) It is through language that humans express their innermost desires, thoughts, and sentiments. The ability to communicate and interact with others in social settings is reliant on a shared linguistic basis. By studying a person's language, you can learn a lot about their emotions and desires. The spoken and written forms of language are employed in a wide variety of contexts, including but not limited to everyday conversation, formal and informal learning, and scientific inquiry. Because of their critical nature, languages are taught in formal settings like schools, colleges, and universities as well as in informal ones like workshops and seminars. Around the world, teaching ESL is a formidable task. English is widely used in all forms of media and print, from television and radio to print publications like periodicals and encyclopedias. People who want to learn about science and technology should learn this language well because it is used in almost every country in these fields.

In the Indian state of West Bengal, English is a compulsory subject at all levels of schooling, including elementary, middle, and high schools, as well as colleges and universities. It has been taught because English is very important for a student's future, and the government has always tried to enhance the standard of English teaching in government schools compared to private schools. Because of this progress, English is now one of the subjects tested on all national exams, including Bank, Railway, UPSC, IAS, IPS, WBCS, UGC NET, etc. Every student will be able to talk to others and say what they think, feel, and want. This will improve their chances of getting a job, and the curriculum needs to be changed to make sure students speak English. The main goal of the English language curriculum in India's junior and senior high schools is to encourage speaking. The kids continue to be bad at speaking English. This shows us that we need to do more to improve their (students') ability to communicate orally. To achieve this goal, we need to improve the way we teach, which should be reflected in both what we teach and how we teach it to the students. Brown (1991) says that "the next big change in how languages were taught happened during World War II." The US military realised it needed fast language learners at this point. The "Army Method"—an intensive language course that emphasises oral and aural skills—has emerged as a means to improve translation communication. He goes on to say that this combination, along with some major theories about learning languages from the fields of linguistic descriptive psychology and behavioural psychology, is called the Audio-Lingual Method (ALM).

Literature Review:

Since elementary school, learning a foreign language involves listening, reading, writing, and speaking. Students struggle to speak English. Speaking is the productive aural/oral ability, according to Nunan (2003: 48), and it comprises generating coherent verbal utterances to impart meaning. Approx. 10k to 12k words are used daily by the average person. Speaking is the capability to make sounds that have sensible meaning and can be comprehend in order to communicate well. "States that speaking is the verbal use of language to communicate with others" Fulcher (2003:23). Today's students often pause, lose ideas, and seem hesitant to make mistakes when speaking. Few learners speak English, and when they do, they frequently use poor grammar. Additionally, few students think that knowing English is not necessary and that they can get by and get work without it. The teacher's lack of motivational engagement during the speaking session may be the cause of this perception. "Engaging in

interactive discourse with a fellow language speaker to achieve pragmatic goals through effective communication.” Hughes (2001: 73)

Other student activities frequently dominate other issues that arise in speaking classes. There are numerous activities available to motivate and engage students in learning English. To overcome these difficulties, the children can learn to speak using the Audio-Lingual method. The English educator must be beware to use some unique approaches and carefully chosen teaching methodologies, particularly when it comes to developing speaking abilities. The audio-linguistic approach to teach spoken English is too consistent with studying and speaking teaching methodologies. It is too authentic and can give the right answer immediately. In one hand the direct and audio-linguistic method is similar to, which also relies on vocal communication. The Audio-Lingual Method, on the other, is fundamentally different in that it focuses on teaching students how to use grammatical sentence patterns rather than focusing on vocabulary learning through context exposure. Furthermore, the audio-lingual method is fully dedicated in linguistic and physiological theories, setting it apart from the Direct Method, which lacks such a strong theoretical foundation.

The audio-linguistic approach to spoken English instruction aligns more closely with effective learning and teaching methodologies. It offers a greater sense of authenticity and immediate access to accurate answers. It also has a powerful theoretical foundation in language and physiology, whereas the Direct Method does not. The Department English of the HKBP Nommensen University had conducted a research programme on the goal of the problem is to determine how the ALM affects speaking abilities of 2nd grade student. The focus of this study is on developing speaking skill, which includes

Vocabulary, pronunciation, fluency, comprehension and grammar, according to Scoot, (2005:90-91) To optimise autonomous language use, speaking tasks must be productive. Scoot optimises linguistic autonomy by incorporating speaking task criteria into productivity and language productivity. The speaking activity has a clear goal can often boost purposefulness and language production, especially when it calls for collaboration among the students to accomplish the objective. Interaction in the class between teacher and students should be required in case of fruitful communication.

One of the most useful ALM guidelines is imitation. In the beginning stages of learning a language, students learn by imitating their teachers and peers. It's just how kids form habits normally. Practice with phonological or grammatical aspects of the language can be achieved through intensive speaking, which includes imitation.

Many classroom conversations consist of quick responses to either teacher- or peer-initiated inquiries or observations. A more advanced form of responsive language is transactional language, which is used to transmit or exchange specific information. Interpersonal dialogue, on the other hand, is more about keeping friendships alive than about learning something new. The instructor gives the students a model to imitate, and they are to do so as swiftly and accurately as they can. This exercise is frequently utilised in the process of teaching the lines of the dialogue. The term "chain drill" refers to the line of questioning and answering that develops while pupils work together. The instructor initiates the chain by greeting or questioning a specific student. This student then directs his remark to the student seated next to him. The chain continues as the first student greets and asks a question of the second student. A chain drill permits some regulated communication, but in a restricted capacity. Additionally, a chain exercise allows the instructor to evaluate each student's speech. The teacher uses word pairings that differ by one sound, like "chip" and "cheap." Students first compare the two words. The teacher chooses which sounds to work on based on a contrastive examination of the student's native and target languages. The objective of the method is also providing students with meaningful practise of a particular grammatical concept.

Objectives, Research Questions and Hypothesis

- To identify the reason behind students are not occupying the English speaking skill.
- To find out whether or not the ELT classes are interactive.
- To assess how the ALM helps to improves English communication abilities through listening and speaking.

The researchers' working hypothesis was that the use of the audio-lingual teaching method would have a substantial impact on the improvement of the students' English language competence, and this premise motivated the entire study. For faster comprehension, the practise may work better while listening.

Method

The research was set up in a way that was both experimental and quantitative. There were two variables, such as speaking ability as a dependent variable and an Audio-Lingual Method as an independent variable. Experimental research is the traditional method used in science labs, according to Best (2002: 133), where variables may be controlled and effects can be observed and manipulated. The researcher used two study groups in this experimental research: the experimental and the control group. The experimental group used the audio-lingual method to teach speaking, while the control group did not use the audio-lingual method. The researcher will use stratified random sampling to select a homogeneous sample of 40 students from both the 10th and 12th grades in both genders (Girls and Boys). The speaking test was carried out orally to collect the data. The teacher called on each student individually to come to the front of the class and give a speech based on the topic he had assigned. Since the performance of the students was recorded during the test, the researcher asked the students to speak clearly. Before beginning the Audio-Lingual Method teaching process, the author administered the same pre-test to the experimental and control groups. The primary research was conducted using a two-questionnaire survey. We prepared eight research questions for students and sixteen questions for teachers, including strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, and strongly agreed in the questionnaire for the pretest and eight questions more for students for the posttest survey. We assessed listening and speaking abilities, as well as classroom observations and face-to-face student and teacher interviews. Surveys questions were given to ten students in each class. The data was analysed both qualitatively and quantitatively with the help of IBM SPSS 25 SOFTWARE and the inherent patterns in the data were interpreted using an appropriate explanation in response to the questions.

Analysis of Data:

Readers can look at the following statistics in order to get a reasonable knowledge of the disparities in scores that exist between the control and the experimental group of students:

Descriptive Statistics

Name of the Test	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
CGPOSTTEST	20	54	67	58.75	3.537
EGPOSTTEST	20	61.00	79.00	68.7000	4.31765
Valid N (List Wise)	20				

According to the descriptive statistics presented in the preceding table, the reader may see a discernible difference in the mark distribution between the post-test results of both groups. It is evident from these data that the mean post-test score of the experimental group is 9.95% greater than the control group. There is a difference in the Standard Deviation also between control group (3.537) and experimental group (4.31765).

Pair 1	CGPRETES T – CGPOSTTE ST	-2.20000	0.7677 7	0.1716 8	- 2.55933	- 1.84067	- 12.81 5	1 9	0.000
Pair 2	EGPRETES T – EGPOSTTE ST	- 11.3500 0	2.6412 7	0.5906 1	- 12.5861 5	- 10.1138 5	- 19.21 8	1 9	0.000

In both pairs the readers can noticed that the sig. value is less than .005 in paired samples test that means there is significant improvement in speaking English ability in the use of audio – lingual method instead of others a method.

Now, the researcher intends to present a pre-test questionnaire to the control group in order to present a realistic scenario about current teaching methods and collect Students responses to the following questions.

Questionnaire

SPSS Pre-Test Questionnaire Frequency Test

Do you believe that fear and uneasiness among the pupils are preventing them from developing their English speaking skills?

Do you believe that your present teaching method does not provide an English-speaking setting that makes it simpler for you to learn the language?

Do you believe that fear and uneasiness among the pupils are preventing them from developing their English speaking skills?

Do you believe that if your teacher taught in English, it would make it simpler for you to speak intelligibly?

Descriptive Frequency Test

N	Valid	20	20	20	20	20
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
	Mean	4.1000	4.0500	3.5500	4.2000	3.7500
	Median	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000	4.0000
	Mode	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00

After conducting the research described above and analysing the data, the researcher came to the conclusion that the current teaching technique is less effective than ALM in terms of enhancing students' English speaking abilities. The majority of the twenty students who are a part of the control group select answer number 4, which is "Agree." The respective “mean” score of the test is around 4 which means “Agree”

After teaching the experimental group with the ALM method, the researcher asked the following questions and found significant differences in the student answers given below:

SPSS Pre-Test Questionnaire Frequency Test

Does the idea of learning English using an audio-lingual method seem interesting to you?

Do you feel that ALM helps you to remember your speech in a way that you can use spontaneously?

Is the use of this strategy helpful in increasing the degree of confidence needed for public speaking?

Does ALM help you in influence speaking ability in english more faster then Grammar and Translation Method?

Descriptive Frequency Test

N	Valid	20	20	20	20	20
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
	Mean	Mean	3.8500	3.8000	3.7000	3.7500
	Median	Median	3.8235 ^a	3.7647 ^a	3.6667 ^a	3.7647 ^a
	Mode	Mode	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00

After conducting the research described above and analysing the data, the researcher came to the conclusion that ALM has a considerable influence on improving students' English speaking abilities. The majority of the students in the experimental group, which consists of twenty students, selected answer number 4 ('Agree'). The responses had means of 3.8500, 3.8000, 3.7000, 3.7500, and 3.9500 respectively; all of these are quite close to 4, which indicate

that respondents are in agreement that ALM assists them more in improving their ability to speak English.

The Research Results and Findings.

According to the results of this research, students often have trouble speaking because they don't know enough words. They often pause during their speech to think of what they want to say. It was also found that when students speak in an upward communication style, they are nervous on the inside. They are even better at writing and reading and can explain their concerns better in their first language, Bengali, but they don't know how to listen or talk well in English. Students don't get to be around people who speak English, which makes it hard for them to get into the habit of speaking English well. Most of the time, they were taught by grammar and the translation method, which seems more complicated than the ALM and the direct method. Most of the time, the researcher found that the person knew how to use grammar but couldn't find the right words to show how they felt to their audience. At the start of the orientation test, students often feel nervous about how they will learn with ALM. During the first cycle, they felt that there was a gap between the teacher and the students. When the researcher tested ALM for the second time, the results were better than the first time.

An observation sheet, diary notes, and question sheet were also used to get information. Students were more involved in the teaching and learning process, as shown by observation sheets and diary entries. At first, not every student was interested in learning. During the teaching and learning process, there were some students who talked. Aside from that, when they were given the chance to say something about the topic, they were still shy. But at the next meeting, both the students who asked questions and those who answered them showed how much they cared. The survey also showed that most of the students strongly agreed that ALM is an excellent way to teach conversation. All of those numbers showed that the students had good attitudes and responses while they were being taught. Lastly, both quantitative and qualitative data showed that students' success in the ALM had a much better effect on their ability to communicate than the current teaching methods. ALM is a method to teach a language that is based on the behaviorist principle. The new information is presented in the form of a conversation, drills are done over and over, and a set of phrases needs to be

learned in repetitive way, and so on. The objective of this techniques is to teach students how to communicate well by giving them a lot of practice and repetition in secondary schools. The ALM can reduce the lack of conversational components or improve their speaking abilities. Comparing control and experimental group pretest and post-test scores demonstrates it very clearly.

Conclusion and Recommendations.

According to the study, the researcher thinks that the Audio-Lingual Method had a huge impact on the students' ability to speak in Bengali and other vernacular medium schools. When the ALM is used to teach, the students' speaking skills are better than when the Audio-Lingual Method is not used. But, even though the results show that there were problems at the start of the teaching process, these problems have been fixed by the habit-building with drill method in subsequent stages. However, despite the fact that the results indicate challenges at the beginning of the teaching process, these issues have been remedied as a result of the habit-building with drill approach in subsequent stages.

It is recommended that English teachers, especially in Bengali and other vernacular medium schools, employ the Audio-Lingual Method to enhance their students' English speaking skills. Fluency in English will help them develop their personalities so they can occupy prestigious jobs in the near future. Other researchers are recommended if they wish to examine the efficiency of the Audio-Lingual Method in enhancing speaking skills through a further study or can conduct research to explore the new dimensions.

References

1. Ahmed, M. S. "The English Language Teaching (ELT) in the Secondary Schools in Assam." *International Journal of English language, literature and Humanities* 4.3 (2016): 219223.
2. Kothari, Chakravanti Rajagopalachari. *Research methodology: Methods and techniques*. New Age International, 2004. B
3. Crystal, David. *English as a global language*. Cambridge university press, 2003.
4. Larsen-Freeman, Diane. *Techniques and principles in language teaching*. oxford University, 2000.
5. Brown, H. Douglas. *Principles of language learning and teaching*. Vol. 4. New York: Longman, 2000.
6. Anthony, Edward M. "Approach, method and technique." *English language teaching* 17.2 (1963): 63-67.
7. Anderson-Mejias, Pamela L. "English for academic listening: Teaching the skills associated with listening to extended discourse." *Foreign Language Annals* 19.5 (1986): 391-398.
8. Bera, K. K. *Impact of Audio-Lingual Materials on English Communication Skills: A Case Study of College Students in Kolkata*.
9. Chakrabarty, A. K. 'Second Language Teaching through Audio Lingual Method and Conventional Approach at Upper Primary Level of Birbhum District: An Experimental Study'. *International Journal in Management & Social Science*, vol. 4, no. 6, 2016, pp. 341–349.
10. Chastain, K. *The Development of Modern Language Skills: Theory to Practice*. The Centre for Curriculum Development. 1971.
11. Decanny, F. R. *Techniques and Procedures in Second Language Teaching*. Phoenix Publishing House, 1963.

12. Larsen-Freeman, Diane. *Techniques and Principles in Language Teaching*. 2nd ed., Oxford University Press, 2000. *Teaching Techniques in English as a Second Language S*.
13. Moulton, W. G. 'Linguistics and Language Teaching in the United States, 1940-1960'. *Trends in European and American Linguistics 1930-1960*, edited by C. Mohrann et al., Spectrum Publishers, 1961, pp. 86–89.
14. Nagaraj, G. *English Language Teaching: Approaches, Methods, Techniques*. 2008.
15. Richards, Jack C., and Theodore S. Rodgers. *Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching Create EBook*. 2nd ed., Cambridge University Press, 2017. Cambridge Language Teaching Library.
16. Rivers, Wilga M. *Psychologist and the Foreign Language Teacher*. University of Chicago Press, 1977.
17. Shaikh, F. S. 'Effective Methods of Teaching English as a Second Language in the Classroom'. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, vol. 4, no. 2, 2015, pp. 979–984.
18. Saraswathi, V. 'English Language Teaching: Principles and Practice'. Orient Longman, 2004.
19. Scrivener, J. *Learning Teaching: A Guidebook for English Language Trainers*. Macmillan, 2005.
20. Skinner, B. F. *Verbal Behavior*. Blurb, 2022.
21. Weston, J. *The Tape Recorder in the Classroom*. National Committee for AudioVisual Aids in Education. 196